

CREATING DATABASE OF BASIS WORDS

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Abstract. *For many foreign language learners and schoolchildren, learning the Uzbek language is very convenient when divided into levels. Based on this idea, we considered the issue of automatically extracting basis words from Uzbek texts. For this purpose, a School Corpus was created based on 61 textbooks approved by the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In addition, a Synonym Corpus was developed based on Azim Khojayev's book "Uzbek Language Synonyms Dictionary". High-frequency and lemma comparative extraction methods were used to extract basis words.*

Keywords: *sentiment analysis, high-frequency, stopword lists, stop-word removal, natural phenomena.*

Introduction

For Uzbek language learners, the language learning process involves various stages. The most important of these is memorising words. That is, first of all, the learner must memorise Uzbek words and understand their meaning. It is necessary to identify the most necessary words and start learning these words first. The problem arises of learning these words step by step. To solve this problem, it is advisable to start learning the Uzbek language by studying basis words. Therefore, we need to consider the issue of determining the table of basis words. First of all, it is natural to ask what basis words are? A set of basis words is a set such that all words in the Uzbek language can be expressed using these words. That is, basis words are the word formation that forms the basis of the Uzbek language, a unit used in linguistic analysis processes, and also expressing the main meaning of a sentence. We can also consider a basis word as a unit that can replace several words. That is, we will consider the issue of forming a set of necessary words in the Uzbek language.

In general, in this work, we considered the issue of forming a basis of words divided into levels for the levels of knowledge of the Uzbek language. We adapted this process to suit primary school students (grades 1-4) and 5th- and 6th-grade students. As a result, we answered the question of how many basis words students in grades 1-6 should know for each school grade.

Related Work

The selection of educational materials for primary school students according to their intellectual potential is one of the problems of the education system. This article [1] considers the issue of creating a school corpus to determine the intellectual potential of primary school students based on school textbooks. The educational corpus was created on the basis of 35 primary school textbooks approved by the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The problem was completely solved on the basis of textbooks based on the primary Uzbek language. The technique of identifying basis words based on this Uzbek primary school corpus was studied in the work [2]. The high-frequency method and comparison methods were

used to identify basis words. If basis words are considered the foundation for school students, it is concluded that each school student should know how many basis words across grades.

The main objective of this study [3] is to determine the number of new words that primary school students should acquire during each academic year. To do this, the authors created two types of data sets: the first is based on the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” (EDUL), and the second is the “Uzbek Primary School Corpus” (UPSC), which consists of 35 textbooks from grades 1–4 approved by the Ministry of Preschool and School Education. Using the “Comparative Lemma Separation” (CLEM) method proposed by the authors, grades 1–4 dictionaries were formed and the number of new words needed for each year was determined, without taking into account the morphologically rich word forms of the Uzbek language. It is emphasized that choosing appropriate literary works for secondary school students in grades 5–9 is very important for maintaining their interest and intellectual development. In this article [4], a new approach based on natural language processing (NLP) methods is proposed to improve the literature selection process. We created a special “School Literature Corpus” consisting of Uzbek school fiction textbooks, pre-processed the texts, created a unique dictionary, and transformed them into vectors using TF IDF. The cosine similarity method was used to determine the most suitable books for each grade.

The results obtained show that NLP techniques significantly improve the process of selecting relevant literature, which serves to enrich the curriculum and increase the level of student mastery. The volume of information is constantly increasing due to the rapid development of the Internet and electronic services, but due to time constraints, we do not have the opportunity to read all this information. Even analysing texts in any field requires a lot of work. To solve these problems, the task of automatic text reduction is of great importance. This paper [5] presents an experiment on the text summarisation task in Uzbek. The proposed methodology is based on the TF-IDF algorithm, which identifies semantically important fragments in the text. Then, using the n-gram method, a summary of the text is formed from them. A special corpus called “School corpus” was created to evaluate the proposed method.

The experimental results show that this approach effectively reduces texts in Uzbek and can be widely used in the fields of information retrieval and natural language processing. This dataset aims to solve the problem of automatic detection of stop words in the natural language processing (NLP) process in the resource-limited Karakalpak language. To do this, in this work [6] we created the “Karakalpak Language School Corpus” (KAASC) corpus, which consists of 23 Karakalpak school textbooks. Using KAASC, we created stopword lists using three TF IDF-based methods—unigram, bigram, and collocation. The collected dataset includes these lists and the URLs used to collect the corpus. This paper [7] conducts a study on sentiment analysis of Uzbek restaurant-related texts. The study created a corpus of 8,210 comments based on Google Maps reviews of restaurants in Tashkent, of which 4,500 were positive and 3,710 were negative. The comments were transcribed into the Latin alphabet and subjected to preprocessing steps such as cleaning, stop-word removal, and lexicon-free stemming. In model testing, logistic regression (with n-grams of words and characters) showed the highest accuracy - 91%.

The results of the SVM, RNN, and CNN models were in the range of 88–89%. This work [8] "UzbekVerbDetection: Rule-based Detection of Verbs in Uzbek Texts" by Maksud Sharipov, Elmurod Kuriyozov, Ollabergan Yuldashev, and Ogabek Sobirov proposes a rule-based approach for verb detection in Uzbek texts. This approach relies on a set of rules based on affixes and suffixes to detect morphological patterns of verb forms, taking into account the agglutinative

characteristics of the Uzbek language. The proposed method was tested on a set of 25,000 Uzbek texts and achieved an F1 score of 0.97, which shows its superiority over existing methods. This approach is effective in verb detection, especially considering the complex morphology and affixation system of the Uzbek language, and can be applied to natural language processing tasks such as machine translation, text reduction, and sentiment analysis. Future work may focus on identifying more complex patterns and increasing the generalization ability of the model by exploring machine learning approaches, such as deep learning and transfer learning.

For people learning English as a second language (ESL), it is very important to choose and use the right words to help them communicate and learn. This study [9] looks at how often English words are used in three official English textbooks for grades 7–9 published by the Indonesian Ministry of Culture and Education. The results of the study showed that: The textbooks have enough vocabulary to understand simple and illustrated texts, but not enough to learn real texts. The number of high-frequency words in the first thousand, second thousand, and academic levels is not enough. The number of times a word is repeated in textbooks is not likely to make students remember words at random, unless teachers and students use other methods to learn language.

H. S. Al Qunayeer's article[10] "An Investigation of the Relationship between Reading Comprehension, Vocabulary Knowledge, and English Language Proficiency Level of Saudi EFL Learners," published in the journal *Advances in Language and Literary Studies* in 2021, examines the relationship between reading comprehension, vocabulary knowledge, and English language proficiency level of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students in Saudi Arabia. Objectives and Methodology: The study involved 75 intermediate and advanced English translation students. Their language proficiency level was previously determined through the Oxford Placement Test (OPT). Participants were given tests measuring vocabulary breadth (number of words) and depth (level of knowledge about words), as well as reading comprehension tests. The article [11] analyzes the methodology and technological foundations of creating the Uzbek WordNet. The authors proposed an automated acquisition method based on the Turkish WordNet. In addition, a system was created that represents the lexical-semantic structure of the Uzbek language in digital form. This approach was chosen taking into account the fact that the Uzbek language belongs to the Turkic language family. In the work, Uzbek lexical units, their semantic relationships (for example, synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy) are identified and modeled in the form of a network.

Theory

Data preparation.

In this study, the Synonym Corpus(SYNC) and the School Corpus(SC) were necessary to extract basis words from Uzbek texts.

One of the most important elements is the SC. The SC was prepared in 2 types.

- 1) Uzbek Primary School Corpus (UPSC) - includes textbooks for grades 1-4
- 2) Uzbek Basic Secondary School Corpus (UBSSC) - includes textbooks for grades 5-6

Table 1: Number of books for each grade

Grades	Number of books
1-grade	9
2-grade	9
3-grade	9
4-grade	8

5-grade	13
6-grade	13

UPSC and UBSSC together constitute SC. UPSC - includes textbooks for grades 1-4, and includes lemmas from a total of 35 textbooks. UBSSC - consists of lemmas from 26 textbooks for grades 5-6. To form this corpus, all textbooks were downloaded from the elibrary.tdpu.uz website. They include mathematics for the development of calculation; speech development for the development of oral speech; the world around us, studying natural phenomena; music for the development of musical education, reading to increase our vocabulary and creative thinking, and many other subjects. For grades 5-6, there are subjects such as mathematics, computer science, physics, native language and literature for literary sciences, botany, geography and history. They were converted from PDF to TXT.

The existing shortcomings were manually corrected by the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Lemmas were made unique, and their frequencies were determined. A total of 61 textbooks approved by the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been brought into the corpus. It is natural to ask why the basis words were created using the school corpus. Because school textbooks are the main source for the formation of a student's vocabulary, in which a person learns various words related to various fields. The main task of primary education is to provide the student with basic fundamental knowledge in the subjects that he or she needs to study. That is, through this, the student gets acquainted with various subjects and various terms in them. The SC can serve as a base corpus for any student.

Algorithm for extracting basis words from the SC

The SC is presented to us in the form of lemmas related to subjects in classes. We use the high-frequency and comparative lemma extraction methods to extract basis words from SC corpus using the SYNC.

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed model

Each of the aforementioned steps in the above Figure 1 is described in the following subsections. We can extract the basis words through the above algorithm.

- a) *SC, SYNC*: First of all, we can convert the SC and the SYNC from the data frame format to the list format;
- b) *Extract lemmas of the SC*: SC sentences are divided into tokens and their frequencies are calculated. These tokens are compared with the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language using the Comparative Lemma Extraction Method and transformed into lemmas. Tokens require a lot of memory space and processing time. Hence, we choose to use lemmas as a more suitable approach.

Example 1. For the tokens "archaga", "archalaring", "archalar", "archalardan", "archaning", "archasi", "archasining", the lemma "archa" is obtained. Also, the frequencies of all of them are added and put into the lemma "archa".

- c) *Get_basis_dict function:* This function takes the SC and the SYNC as a data frame format and extracts one or more of the synonyms with the highest frequency as the basis word.
- d) *Calc_frequencies function:* This function takes a word from SYNC and searches for it among the lemmas of a single class in the SC if it exists, adds up the frequencies of the words that come from it and writes them as the frequency of this lemma.

As a result of these operations, basis words are extracted in the section of grades 1-4,5,6.

Experimental results.

Table 2: Number of basis words for each grade

Grades	Number of basis words	Total word count
1-grade	2967	3177
2-grade	4679	5119
3-grade	6248	6710
4-grade	7496	8029
5-grade	12183	63340
6-grade	11917	58844

Table 2 above shows the number of basis words by grade, which indicates how many words a student in each grade needs to know. If we look at the categories, a significant increase was observed in almost every grade. Because as a student grows, the number of subjects he studies increases, the amount of information increases, and at the same time, the richness of his vocabulary also increases sharply.

Table 3 below presents a comparative analysis of the basis words of grade 1 and grade 2:

Table 3: Comparison between 1st grade and 2nd grade

Number of Basis words for 1-graders	2967
Number of Basis words for 2-graders	4679
Intersection of number of 1 st and 2 nd graders basis words	1406
The number of new words learned in 2nd grade	2028

Table 3 above shows that a 1st grader will learn 1406 words repeatedly in 2nd grade. It also shows that they will learn 2028 new words across different subjects.

Table 4 below provides a comparative analysis of the basis words of 2nd grade and 3rd grade:

Table 4: Comparison between 2nd grade and 3rd grade

Number of Basis words for 2-graders	4679
Number of Basis words for 3-graders	6248
Intersection of number of 2 nd and 3 th graders basis words	2144
The number of new words learned in 3rd grade	2313

The above 2144 are examples of common words in both classes.

Example 1. Words such as “achchiq(spicy)”, “quruqlik(land)”, “shoshqaloq(rash)”.

The following Table 5 presents a comparative analysis of the basis words of grade 3 and grade 4:

Table 5: Comparison between 3rd grade and 4th grade

Number of Basis words for 3-graders	6248
Number of Basis words for 4-graders	7496
Intersection of number of 3 rd and 4 th graders basis words	2714
The number of new words learned in 4th grade	2354

A 4th grader should learn the following new words:

Example 2: “arxeolog(archaeologist)”, “betgachoparlik(insolence)”, “shashqator(checkerboard)”.

Below is Table 6 showing how many words a 1st grader will learn by the time they reach 4th grade:

Table 6: Comparison between 1st grade and 4th grade

Number of Basis words for 1-graders	2967
Number of Basis words for 4-graders	7496
Intersection of number of 1 st and 4 th graders basis words	1555

The number of new words learned in 4th grade	3513
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And finally, a comparative analysis of grades 5-6:

Table 7: Comparison between 5th grade and 6th grade

Number of Basis words for 5-graders	12183
Number of Basis words for 6-graders	11917
Intersection of number of 5 th and 6 th graders basis words	5814
The number of new words learned in the 6nd grade	6104

At this level, the student learns different regional words and increases his or her vocabulary.

Conclusion

In this study, two main approaches to identifying basis words were used - the high-frequency and the Comparative Lemma Extraction Methods. Although the high-frequency method is effective in extracting many repeated words as the basis element, it sometimes selects a few words with a common meaning as the basis word. The Comparative Lemma Extraction Method helps to bring the words into line with the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language, which prevents the artificial increase in the number of basis words. The language classification process can be carried out using the set of basis words.

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